

《Fatigue life analysis for wind turbine gear shaft with oxide inclusion》

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Abstract

In this paper, the elastic contact finite element model of helical gear pair in the middle stage of wind power increasing box is established. Based on the Brown-Miller criterion and the real load spectrum of wind power growth box, fatigue life of helical gear pair is calculated. Then the influence of tooth surface roughness, residual stress and oxide inclusion on the fatigue life of helical gear pair are studied.

1. Background

Loss of power generation and maintenance costs caused by wind turbine failure are two main components of wind farm operating costs. According to the statistics of wind turbine faults from the Reliability Assessment and Management Center of Royal Swedish Institute of Technology, the related faults of wind turbine transmission chain cause the longest downtime and the greatest impact on power production^[1]. Therefore, reducing the failure rate of wind turbine is the core issue in the design and application process^[1-3]. Recently, several wind turbine gear failure cases show that the oxide inclusion is one of major reasons for the fracture of middle gear shaft under fatigue loading condition.

2. Finite element analysis

Fig.1 Detail of the inclusion zone in gear pair

Fig.2 Stress distribution of the inclusion zone

3. Fatigue life calculation

In this paper, the failure mode of the researched object is high cycle fatigue. Then the nominal stress method is adopted for high cycle fatigue life calculation. Based on the stress of material or structure, life cycle analysis is conducted by rainfall cycle counting method and Palmgerm-Miner linear cumulative damage theory. According to Miner's theory, the formulas for calculating fatigue damage and fatigue life are given as follows:

$$D = \sum_i^l n_i / N_i \quad (1)$$

$$N = 1 / D \quad (2)$$

$$T = \frac{t_s N}{3600 \times 8760} \quad (3)$$

Where l is the Stress level series of variable amplitude load, n_i the Number of cycles at each stress level, N_i limit cycle number of material fatigue failure at different stress levels, D the total fatigue damage, N the fatigue life, T the fatigue life time, year, t_s the fatigue load time, seconds.

Fig.3 Fatigue load 1

Fig.4 Fatigue load 2

4. Predicted results

- Mismatch of mechanical properties;
- Low fatigue life of boundary areas ;
- Inclusion size/position and residual stress have effect on fatigue life.

References

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